

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

TEACHING EXPERIENCES IN AN INCLUSIVE CLASS: A CASE STUDY

Arvina D. Sarmiento

Dean

Mabalacat City College

Mabalacat City, Pampanga, Region 3, Philippines

Abstract

This study explored the experiences of ten elementary teachers (80% female) teaching learners with special needs. All participants had training in inclusive education and worked with diverse learners across grades 2-5. The paper highlights the challenges educators face, including limited resources, communication barriers, and creating inclusive environments. It emphasizes the importance of professional development for teachers, focusing on collaboration, self-care, and strategies to support learners with diverse needs. The proposed inclusive education plan emphasizes a well-structured and supportive classroom environment. Key components include building teacher capacity, fostering collaboration, providing individualized instruction, and prioritizing teacher well-being. This approach aims to empower educators to create an inclusive learning environment where all learners feel valued and can reach their full potential.

Keywords: *teaching experiences, positive, challenges, coping, plan*

Introduction

Since education is viewed as a major factor in growth and development, there is an increasing emphasis on enrolling all pupils in regular schools. This generates challenges as well as opportunities. Nelson Mandela's statement regarding education's ability to transform the world emphasizes teachers' critical role in making this work. A better future is demanded by the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which include universal access to high-quality education (SDG 4). This study examines how educators in traditional classroom settings manage difficulties and foster resilience, particularly emphasizing how these approaches match SDG 4's tenets. The experiences of the elementary teachers at Dau Elementary School will be examined.

This study generally aimed to evaluate and determine the lived experiences of elementary teachers in Dau Elementary School in an inclusive education. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants, focusing on the following aspects:
 - 1.1 sex,
 - 1.2 grade level taught,
 - 1.3 type of learner with special needs taught,
 - 1.4 training/s attended related to Special Education,
 - 1.5 number of years in the service and

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

- 1.6 educational attainment?
2. What are the positive and challenging experiences of the participants in an inclusive class?
3. How did the participants cope with the challenges?
4. Based on the study's findings, what inclusive education plan may be proposed?
5. What are the implications of this study to early childhood education?

Literature

In the Philippines, inclusive education is becoming more popular with the goal of giving all students equitable access to traditional classroom settings with pre-existing policies and resources.

The "Instituting a Policy of Inclusion and Services for Learners with Disabilities in Support of Inclusive Education Act," also known as Republic Act No. 11650 (2022), ensures that students with disabilities have access to high-quality, inclusive, and accessible education. The most recent law requires all educational institutions, public and private, to guarantee students with disabilities fair and equal access to high-quality instruction. It forbids disability discrimination and mandates that educational institutions make appropriate accommodations.

Section 21 of DepEd Order No. 2019: A framework for inclusive education is included in the DepEd Order that describes the Policy Guidelines on the K–12 Basic Education Program. It highlights every Filipino's entitlement to high-quality, fair, and culturally relevant education. It emphasizes that every Filipino, regardless of background, has the right to a well-rounded education by integrating inclusive education throughout the K–12 curriculum.

The Enhanced Basic Education Act, Republic Act No. 10533 (2013), and its Implementing Rules and Regulations mandate programs that serve the diverse needs of students from different backgrounds, including those with impairments. This encourages inclusivity within basic education. By requiring programs that address the many needs of students, it establishes the foundation for inclusivity in basic education. Together, these laws help to build a more inclusive Philippine educational system.

A study by PZJ Raguindin (2021) examined the role of collaboration and support networks among teachers in Philippine elementary schools that practice inclusive education. They found that collaborative efforts among teachers, along with adequate support from school management, contributed significantly to their resilience and effectiveness in inclusive classrooms.

This local study provides insights into the importance of school-level support systems, which is highly relevant to the research on resilience among teachers at Dau Elementary School. Allam & Martin (2021) discussed that education for students with special needs, evolving from special education to inclusive education, aligns with global efforts toward inclusive societies, as emphasized by Allam and Martin. Despite supportive guidelines and policies, challenges persist in schools fostering inclusivity.

In the Philippines, SPED is a prominent topic, echoing the worldwide push for inclusive education. However, effective implementation often lags behind, despite the presence of supportive policies. Their study highlights the importance of addressing the hurdles encountered by SPED teachers when educating children with learning disabilities. This study probes into issues such as teachers' challenges, teaching strategies, and collaboration with administrators and parents, closely mirroring the objectives of the study.

Quizana and Espiritu's study (2023) conducted in Quezon's third congressional district revealed that teachers in SPED Inclusive Education Programs handled learners with Autism

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Spectrum Disorders, ADHD, and Dyslexia. They employed teaching strategies such as positive reinforcement and individualized instruction. Challenges encompassed behavioral issues, communication hurdles, and limited parental involvement. Coping strategies included differentiated instruction and emotional understanding. This study is with the study, as it underlines the practical challenges faced by teachers in the Philippine context and how these challenges are managed.

Conceptual Framework

The diagram likely presents a conceptual framework for understanding the factors that influence teachers' experiences in inclusive classrooms. It likely includes three main components.

The diagram explores the various aspects of teaching in an inclusive classroom. It includes information on the demographics of teachers, their positive and challenging experiences, coping mechanisms they employ, and the potential implications of inclusive education. By understanding these factors, educators can better prepare to create effective and inclusive learning environments.

METHOD

The purpose of this qualitative research study was to investigate the experiences of elementary teachers dealing with special needs learners. The study used a case study design to provide a comprehensive illustration of the experiences of teachers working with various cases of pupils with special needs. The researchers used the intrinsic case study approach to investigate the resilience of teaching experiences working with learners with special needs in a typical classroom. The study was conducted at Dau Elementary School, a large institution with many teachers responsible for managing learners with disabilities in a traditional classroom setting. The participants of the study were ten elementary teachers who were working with pupils with special needs. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with each participant to get data relevant to the research aim. The researcher made sure the study instrument was validated first. The researcher then obtained authorization from the Mabalacat City Department of Education Division and commenced the study's execution and data collection process.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Results

Teaching experiences of elementary teachers in an inclusive class at Dau elementary school. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that:

1. The ten participants in the training were predominantly female (80%, n=8) with only 2 males (20%). Grade level distribution was even with 3 participants each handling Grades 2 and 4, and 2 participants each for Grades 3 and 5. All participants worked with students with special needs, with 2 participants per grade level equipped to support these students. In terms of training, all participants had undergone sessions on SPED Implementation, Upskilling/Retooling for Inclusive Education, and SPED Content and Pedagogy. Teaching experience ranged from 6 to 39 years, with the most experienced educators having 39 years under their belt. The majority held a Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd), with one participant possessing a Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd).
2. The teaching profession offers a unique blend of challenges and rewards. While teachers experience the joy of witnessing student growth, building relationships, and fostering a love of learning, they also face hurdles like limited resources, communication barriers, and creating inclusive environments. Support for teachers through professional development, collaboration with families, and a focus on self-care can help them navigate these challenges and find fulfillment in their work.
3. Educators face a complex challenge in supporting learners with learning disabilities. Limited resources and parental involvement can make it difficult to provide individualized help. Communication barriers, social-emotional difficulties, and the need for tailored lessons all add to the pressure. However, educators can overcome these hurdles through collaboration with support staff, utilizing positive reinforcement techniques, and prioritizing self-care. Building trust with students, establishing clear expectations, and offering a structured yet flexible classroom environment is also key. Finally, collaborating with parents and specialists, finding accessible materials, and leveraging technology can empower educators to create a successful learning experience for all learners.
4. Based on the findings of the study a proposed inclusive education plan is a well-structured and supportive classroom environment is essential for teachers with learners in an inclusive classroom to thrive. This includes learners with diverse learning needs, backgrounds, and abilities. By building capacity, fostering a supportive environment, providing individualized instruction, and prioritizing educator well-being, we can create a classroom where every student feels safe, challenged, and empowered to reach their full potential.
5. By understanding the challenges and rewards of teaching with special needs, and by implementing effective coping strategies, early childhood educators can create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment for all children.

Recommendations

From the findings and conclusions of this study, the succeeding is highly suggested:

1. Due to the high number of female participants and even distribution across grade levels, future trainings could be opened to a broader range of genders and potentially target specific grade levels based on identified needs or areas for improvement.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

2. Given the demanding yet rewarding nature of teaching, schools and districts should prioritize supporting educators through professional development opportunities, fostering collaboration with families, and promoting teacher well-being initiatives.
3. Educators can overcome the challenges of supporting learners with learning disabilities by collaborating with support staff, utilizing positive reinforcement techniques, prioritizing self-care, building trust with students, establishing clear expectations, offering a structured yet flexible classroom environment, collaborating with parents and specialists, finding accessible materials, and leveraging technology. This creates a successful learning experience for all learners.
4. Implement a well-structured and supportive classroom environment by referring to the proposed inclusive education plan to improve the success of inclusive education for students with diverse needs. This environment should prioritize building teacher capacity, fostering collaboration, providing individualized instruction, and ensuring educator well-being.
5. Early childhood education programs should provide training on the challenges and rewards of teaching students with special needs, along with effective coping strategies. This will equip educators to create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment for all children.

REFERENCES

- Abraham, J. (2021). Self-efficacy and the inclusive teacher. *Educational Information Graduate Center Studies*, 13(1), 47-51. [Available online at ERIC database: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1303965>]
- Acharya, N., & Rodriguez, D. (2021). Fostering creativity for students with special needs through innovative learning environments. *Journal of Leadership in Instruction*, 26-31.
- Accardo, A., et al. (2020). Special education teacher preparation and family collaboration. *School Community Journal*, 30(2), 53-72.
- Aldabas, R. (2020). Special education teachers' perceptions of preparedness to teach students with severe disabilities in inclusive classrooms. *Education and Training*, 10(3), 1-14. doi: 10.1177/2158244020950657
- Allam, F., & Martin, M. (2021). Issues and challenges in special education: A qualitative analysis from teacher's perspective. *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*, 10(1), 37-49. doi: 10.37134/saecj.vol10.1.4.2021
- Almutairi, N. R. (2018). Effective reading strategies for increasing the reading comprehension level of third-grade students with learning disabilities (Doctoral dissertation). Western Michigan University. [Available online at Scholar Works at WMU: <https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/dissertations/3247/>]
- Baptist Okech, J. B., Yuwono, I., & Juma Abdu, W. (2021). Implementation of inclusive education practices for children with disabilities & other special needs in Uganda. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 8(1), 97-102. doi: 10.20448/journal.509.2021.81.97.102

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.277-283 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Bariroh, S. (2018). The influence of parents' involvement on children with special needs' motivation and learning achievement. *International Education Studies*, 11(4), 96- 114. doi: 10.5539/ies.v11n4p96

Batur, Z., Başar, M., & Nilüfer Süzen, H. (2019). Critical visual reading skills of students. *International Journal of Educational Literacy Studies*, 7(3), 38-48. doi: 10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.7n.3p.38 46

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13379025

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.